

Increasing the effectiveness of learning biology lessons by means of interactive games and interactive methods

She is a 4th grade student of the biology department of Karshi State University

Nuriddinova Sevinch Nuriddin kizi

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute, Department of Biology

2nd grade student

Nuriddinova Nozima Nuriddin kizi

Abstract: The purpose and tasks of biology teaching methodology. The methodology of teaching biology is about learning, processes, principles and laws related to the fundamentals of biological science, educational processes related to the fundamentals of biological science. Information and instructions on increasing the effectiveness of learning biology lessons by means of interactive games and interactive methods are presented.

Key words: Methodology, task, development, science, program, skills, interactive games, interactive method, technology.

One of the requirements of the "National Personnel Training Program" of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the widespread use of new pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, and the acceleration of training using the modular system of training.

The purpose and tasks of biology teaching methodology. Biology teaching methodology is the science of learning, processes, principles and laws related to the basics of biology. Knowledge of these principles and laws allows the teacher to organize and manage educational processes related to the school biology course in accordance with the requirements of the time. The biology teaching methodology aims to introduce the content of biology subjects, its teaching forms, methods, and tools in an interdependent manner. The main task of the biology teaching methodology is to provide students with in-depth knowledge of biological subjects, to develop the content of subjects, teaching forms, tools and methods that help them grow as well-rounded individuals. consists of output. Any science is related to the research activity of a person, it is aimed at gathering knowledge about things and phenomena, and the object of research is devoted to obtaining complete and deep knowledge about the phenomena. The main function of science is research. The methodology of teaching biology as a science aims to study the learning, education and development of students related to this science from a theoretical and practical point of view. Knowing the goals of teaching biology gives the teacher the opportunity to control the teaching process.

The tasks of teaching methodology of biology as a science are as follows:

1. Determining the place of educational science in the education and upbringing of students;
2. Develop recommendations for improving school curricula and textbooks and apply them to school practice;

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-7

3. Determining the content of academic subjects and the consistency of learning of the subjects in accordance with the age of the students;
4. Development of teaching methods and organizational forms, taking into account the specific aspects of biological subjects;
5. Determining the necessary equipment for use in the teaching process. The biology room is a living corner, the organization of the experimental land area, the designation of natural, pictorial, dynamic, audio, video tools.

Until now, as a result of the pedagogical experiments carried out in the methodology of teaching biology, "Development of biological concepts", "System of forms of teaching in biology", "Methods of teaching in biology", "Development of ecological concepts in biology", "Development of biological concepts" theories such as "material base system", "methodical training system of student biologists of Pedagogical institutions for school work" were developed and put into practice.

For this purpose, today's teacher is required to be a creative, inquisitive teacher who teaches students using new pedagogical technologies. The use of interactive methods in biology lessons not only increases the effectiveness of the lesson, but also encourages students to search, use additional materials, and make them browse the auxiliary literature. Today, in a number of developed countries, the methods that form the basis of great experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies guaranteeing the effectiveness of the educational process are called interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most common and widely used methods in all types of educational institutions. When choosing interactive methods of teaching, the purpose of education, the number and capabilities of students, the educational and material conditions of the educational institution, the duration of education, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc. are taken into account. Interactive methods are also considered to be a modern version of active methods.

The active method is a form of interaction between the teacher and the student, in which the student is not a passive listener, but has the same activity as the teacher. In the active method, the teacher-student relationship is democratic. If the teacher uses active methods in the teaching process, the student is interested in the lesson process, becomes an active participant in it.

The methodology of teaching biology is the study, processes, principles and laws related to the basics of biology:

Biology teaching methodology is closely related to didactics, which is a part of pedagogy. If didactics studies the laws of acquisition of knowledge, skills and competences by students, and it develops teaching theories and principles for all academic subjects in school, then biology teaching methodology is related to biology. develops theoretical and practical issues related to the content, forms, and methods and tools of teaching and training. Biology teaching methodology is closely related to psychology. Because teaching biology is effective only if it is suitable for the age characteristics of students. For example, because the diet is unstable in teenagers, i.e. students of the 5th-6th grade, the biology teacher uses several methods during the lesson and replaces the activities of the students, taking into account the concreteness of their thinking. uses more visual aids. In the upper classes, since the students' attention has stabilized and their abstract thinking has developed, it is enough to conduct lessons in the form of lectures and use one or two methods.

In the methodology of teaching biology, interactive games and interactive methods are used to increase the effectiveness of learning biology lessons in the process of theoretical and practical training of students, not limited to the description of the structure of the school biology course, general

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-7

secondary and secondary special profession - introduces the unique aspects of the organization of biology teaching in vocational institutions, helps to form skills in the use of biology teaching methods and tools, and the skills that students should master allows students to master a minimum set of knowledge. At the same time, modern pedagogy, the use of information technologies, and an innovative approach to teaching biology create skills.

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